

QUALITY INFLUENCE CUSTOMER TO PREFER ROADSIDE TEA STALLS**Dr. Prakash H. Karmadkar***(MMS, Ph.D)**Research Guide and HOD**PE Society's IMCD Research Canter Nigdi, Pune - 44***Abstract :**

*Tea is the most common drink in rural and Urban area of Maharashtra, India. British has introduce tea. This hot drink is a regular, refreshing drink, an excuse for debate. It is always together from the social & economic culture. The various of tea that is made and sold by vendors, the quality of tea that is sold a superior quality. Tea stall opens at 6.30 am to till 8 pm. A chaiwallah keeps making tea. It is actually a strenuous job but the returns are very high. The average income of a chaiwallah is between Rs 2500 and Rs 3500 per day. Researcher found out that the average cost of a bhand of tea in the city is Rs 8-12 and a chaiwallah sells not less than 400 cups of tea per day. There are 100 ways and styles that a tea maker make and serve tea. **Tea break for some refreshment** is given to the employees at industries and corporate offices. It makes a healthy atmosphere for good work culture to the employees. Sip of tea are akin to breaths of energy and freshness for men after their return from work at the evening. Moreover, the tea is serving in family and friends get-together. Senior citizens and the retirees in share a great bond with tea. There is not railway platform without tea stalls in Maharashtra. 1000 of vendors earn a daily income by selling tea in local and express trains Tea packaging is concerned are more popular in the areas, However, depending on circumstances, roadside vendors must comply with zoning and licensing restrictions, health and sanitation. Problems face by consumers are ranked as a) Improper parking facility, b) Unhygienic Conditions of the tea stalls, c) Improper shelf space, d) Selling of other products, e) Unavailability of branded bakery items, f) Lack of knowledge of Retailers, g) Unavailability of desirable products, h) Billing Problems . “Garam chai” is the branding of tea.*

Kay word : Quality, Customer, Place, Price, Roadside tea

Guests are entertained like Gods all over India. Serving tea with some crispy snacks to them is an age-old tradition that is weaved like a thread in the socio-cultural fabric of the country. Offering tea is a token of hospitality in Indian society. Be the season summer, winter, rainy or spring, cups of hot tea with a plateful of snacks like *samosa, kachori, aloo pakoda*, mixture, potato chips, etc. are a must in service to guests in households across the country. Indians of different age groups are in the habit of getting up from bed and starting the day with sips of tea(chai) in the morning. Having tea in the morning is part of their daily routine. The women in Indian households – mothers, wives, or sisters – perform the duty of making morning tea as a habitual action and a token of affection for the family members. The making of tea by them is a sign of their love and care for the other members of the household. Somebody wanted to enjoy a cup of tea at a similar sort of cafe devoted to tea they'd be out of luck, even in the world's second-largest

tea producer -- and a country where people drink nearly eight times more tea than coffee each year. The lack of a single national franchise centered on tea, known in India as chai and served in a glass, has come into especially sharp focus now that coffee giant Starbucks is poised to make its entry into India find nice coffee anywhere, but finding a perfect cup of chai outside is actually tough,” “If it is good quality chai, consumer not mind spending money. People like to see a lot of different flavours of tea, and healthy stuff like green tea.” No matter what people say, much of the problem is image. There are numerous tea vendors who set up shop under a tree or on the streets in India, but the quality of chai they offer for five rupees is often suspect. Pune’s growing urban middle-class would rather pay a few extra rupees for the clean, posh settings offered by coffee shops. In addition, selling tea has been traditionally considered a down-market job. Coffee shops, on the other hand, have always been associated with a Western, fashionable lifestyle. A new wave of educated entrepreneurs hopes to capitalise on this gap, keeping the essence of Indian chai but offering a modern setting. Selling chai is considered the last way of making source of revenue, the fact of the matter is that tea is a very large business in Pune Maharashtra. Roadside tea stalls offer just masala chai, tea brewed with spices and herbs, the former engineer offers a variety including lemon tea and green tea. tea as a healthy drink rich in antioxidants, which can boost the immune system. “People were grateful that we were giving them a clean glass of chai in an affordable and very hygienic setting. Consumers are looking for a change, They have been having coffee at coffee shops for so long, that they were earning for a new concept

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History of Indian Tea or Chai

In the mid-nineteenth century the British administering India began developing tea in Assam Province. Before long they found themselves able to pick up preference over the Chinese estates, and when the new century rolled over Indian tea had the capacity to fulfill half of a majestic tea market. As of now, Indians were not intrigued by the blend devoured by their occupiers yet controlled by the British Indian Tea Association saw another business sector there and chose to utilize it. In order to gain the new clients, basically the average workers, they started to advance the tea that soften ups the magnificent processing plants working in India. Since it was the British they were included in the advancement, they recommended Indians to drink tea with milk and a squeeze of sugar. They additionally began to seem some free road “tea sellers” who attempted to profit on an extravagant item. They changed the extents of milk, sugar and tea and to improve the taste, they were adding solid oriental flavors to the refreshment. Tea Associations endeavors to battle this new exceptionally fizzled and new mix picked up fame in the entire nation. Masala Chai got to be fundamental piece of the way of life and preparing it was perceived as Indian convention. **Tea is the center of the political campaign “Chai Pe Charcha”** (discussion over tea) launched by PM Mr Narendra Modi to connect with the common working-class people at the grassroots level. With the campaign making headlines, tea is now the national flavor of India.

Potential in roadside market

In 1994, Ohio State University published “Ohio Consumer Opinions of Roadside Markets and Farmer’s Markets” based on a random telephone survey of 500 Ohio households. Fifty-five percent of those surveyed shopped at a roadside market during the targeted 12 months (August 1992 through August 1993) and of that group, 64 percent shopped at a roadside market at least four times. However, only 34 percent drove more than 15 minutes to reach those markets; rural and small town dwellers were loathe driving even that far. While 45 percent of non-shoppers concluded farm markets are too far away; 55 percent said they would patronize a farm market if one was conveniently located near their homes. The bottom line: and must set up shop close to customers if business is to thrive. Studies concur that successful roadside stands are located on well-traveled roadways within Pune and PCMC area. They’re situated on the right-hand side of a straight, level stretch. Easy access is a must. Stands adjacent to garden plots or orchards are considered more “farm-like,” thus better, because customers expect that country touch. Ninety percent of consumers 88 percent prefer to buy tea Locating r stand on or adjacent to be good for business. Setting up within easy driving distance of another stand is usually a boon for both. No previous experience direct-marketing, it’s wise to ease into If renovate an indoor structure, allow for consumer comfort. Customers crammed into cramped, close quarters often flee without buying. Five foot or wider aisles are an absolute must. It needs a readily identifiable, an important and frequently overlooked element: simple, eye-catching signs. A University of Tennessee survey of roadside market shoppers indicates 74 percent learn of a stand’s location and another 24 percent via word of mouth; only 2 percent responded to media ads. Primary signs should be placed one-half mile from the stand in both directions and erected following applicable municipal or state regulations. Tea stalls capture the motorist’s eye. Tea stall name and logo along with appropriate mileage are enough. Or simply: Plenty of safe, level, convenient parking is also a needed. where their vehicles won’t block motorists’ views of the stand and its outdoor Quality’s.

Making of Tea

At the season of its innovation there was the same number of formulas for making Masala Chai the same number of sellers in the city of Indian urban areas so until today every Indian family develops its own strategy for setting it up. What’s more, in spite of the fact that there is no exact formula chai will dependably contain:

- Dark, solid tea, which does not annihilate the essence of a sweet-smelling added substances
- milk
- white or chestnut sugar, nectar or molasses
- Flavors: cardamom, cinnamon, ginger, pepper, cloves and some more.

Time commitment

Roadside selling requires a world of time and commitment. accomplish ,enjoy meeting the public—even after spending early morning hours in raw material purchasing Roadside stands are frequently crewed by

younger members. The sorts of employees who man your stand have a dramatic impact on sales. Customers appreciate friendly, courteous cell phones attached to their ears, bored teenagers, and anyone conducting business with snarl or snit, chase away business—big time.

Quality

While someone selling under a shade tree needn't be as design-conscious as a year-round indoor marketer, presentation always counts. Quality, and showcase his finer tea at the scarecrow's feet. Or he might don the scarecrow outfit himself, or dress as a "farm boy. To satisfy the public and spur more sales, savvy stand marketers employ basic Quality techniques like these Create eye appeal by factoring color contrast into arrangements.

Price

Customers demand quality goods, they also expect prices to be somewhat less at a roadside stand. When setting prices, consider quality including higher charges for organically grown produce, competitors' prices, supply and demand, location, customer income and your own production costs and operating expenses. Clearly price every item. Consumers are often reluctant to ask. Provide appropriate signage or mark individual items. Shoppers abhor surprises at the checkout counter. Market researchers claim pricing in fives is considered more farm-like than standard pricing, thus especially appropriate for roadside stands.

Place

Pune city market started showing its potential after the 1960s. 1970s and 80s witnessed its resonance development. And, there are clear indications that are going to see its full growing. In Maharashtra, where research on consumer behavior has been nominal, not much systematized information is available about the rural consumers. Large, it have still to understand the rural consumer, his habits, attitudes and behavior, particularly from the marketing point of view. Getting involved in roadside marketing isn't as simple as most folks think.. Better prices for goods, control over pricing and prompt, direct payment. Stands create jobs for family and friends it costs little to break into roadside retailing when marketers are content to start small and gradually expand. In 1980, there were 15,000 roadside stands in the Pune and PCMC area, that figure almost doubled and it continues to grow.

The locations with the best probability of success are in order:

- Next to colleges and universities, on a commercial *walking* street
- Downtown business district, in a large office building
- Neighborhood commercial *walking* streets
- Heavy foot traffic tourist areas, with great visibility

Objectives of study

1. To identify the demographic profile of the customers unorganized roadside tea shop
2. To analyze the factors which influence consumers to prefer tea shop over roadside tea stall vice-versa

3. To identify the problems faced by consumers from tea shop as well as roadside tea stall.

Limitations of the Study:

In this study Amruthuya Tea Hotel are not cover. The survey has been confined to Pune and Pimpri-Chichwad city only. The sample size was restricted to 150 which are comparatively very less as compared to the entire population of the both city.

Review of literature

Changing consumer preferences, lifestyle and rising income level, which is heavily influenced by economic growth, remains the major driving force for c-store industry in the Asian region. Arshad *et al.*, (2007) have found that dynamics of the demographics, double income, urbanization and internet revolution tilt the consumer's preference towards organized roadside tea shop. Dash *et al.*, (2009) found that consumers in Bangalore coming of growing middle class besides large number of earning youth and increase in spending capacity may favour organized retail but in built deficiencies like inefficiency of distribution channels, internal logistical problem and retail shrinkage may shift the choice towards unorganized retailers.

Methodology

Sample Design: Primary data was collected from 150 respondents (75 shopping from organized roadside tea shop and 75 shopping from unorganized roadside tea shop. These 150 respondents were selected by convenience sampling technique of Probability random sampling

Data Collection: The present study is based on primary data as well as secondary data. The secondary data was drawn from various books, journals, articles, newspapers etc Consumers shopping at organized roadside tea shop and unorganized roadside tea shops were interviewed to collect the primary data. Their answers were further looked into, in some detail to add value to this research.

Statistical Tools Applied: Data collected through survey and interview was analyzed and presented in master table and required sub tables were prepared. For analyzing the data statistical tools like weighted average and percentage method were adopted to find out the customer preferences about various attributes and the dependency between the two variables were worked out and presented in the results.

Area of study

Pune and Pimri-Chichawad is a twin city with many malls and supermarkets and consumers there are expected to be Quality and Taste conscious. Pune and Pimri-Chichawad Customers do not like the taste of tea based drinks because of faulty preparation techniques, they either won't order it again or won't come back. Unfortunately, most of the tea served in this country has no relation to the real thing, and the only way it can be consumed is by drowning its thin, overheated, , the taste of an tea based drink has more to do with the way it is prepared now that most of the tea operations understand how to properly prepare tea .

Table 1 : Factors which influence customer to prefer roadside tea shop

Factors	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neither agree nor Disagree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Total
Quality of products	17/22.66	13/17.33	6/8.00	23/30.66	16/21.33	75/100
Nearness of the Tea stall	45/60.00	27/36.00	3/4.00	-	-	75/100
Status	-	-	7/9.33	42/56.00	26/34.66	75/100
Relations with the shopkeeper e	39/52.00	27/36.00	8/10.66	1/1.33	-	75/100
Choice Product	13/17.33	17/22.66	4/5.33	22/29.33	19/25.33	75/100
Easy availability Of Products	15/20.00	16/21.33	3/4.00	27/36.00	14/18.67	75/100
Supportive Sales personnel	16/21.33	18/24.00	2/2.67	25/33.33	14/18.67	75/100
Proper packaging Of Products (tea)	-	-	4/5.33	44/58.67	27/36.00	75/100
Proper Quality Of the products	6/8.00	8/10.67	5/6.67	33/44.00	23/30.67	75/100
Cleanliness of the stall	7/9.33	8/10.67	5/6.67	3/4.33	21/28.00	75/100
Billing Duration	25/33.33	27/36.00	9/12.00	8/10.67	6/8.00	75/100

Source : Own Study

Table 2 : Problems faced by consumers at Roadside tea stalls

Problems faced by consumer	Agree Score	Rank
Improper parking facility	71.32	I
Unhygienic Conditions of the tea stalls	68.75	II
Improper shelf space	65.6	III
Selling of other products	64.54	IV
Unavailability of branded bakery items	58.78	V
Lack of knowledge of Retailers	55.87	VI
Unavailability of desirable products	45.97	VII
Billing Problems	7.8	VIII

Source : Own Study

Finding

1. Though taste is subjective, most of the customers, when tasting the same one cup made “right”, and the other made following the training guidelines of the operation, will taste the difference and prefer the “right” cup 95% of the time location will be the most important factor in success .
2. The prospective customers can't see tea stall, or access is not convenient, chances of success will be greatly reduced. Some tea stall gross Rs2000-Rs3000 a day, 980% of this revenue coming from tea based drinks, and the owners of these establishments can earn about Rs25, 000 a month in profits.
3. Excellent location, and assuming that everything right, expect to gross anywhere fromRs20,000-Rs30,000 in second month of operation and end up the first full year with overRs500,000 and reach third year Rs3000-Rs8000 per month, this should leave you with 30%-40% of sales after the break-even point.
4. Front line visibility is essential for large accounts, but sales team can benefit from occasional field interactions with the owner. Tea packaging is concerned are more popular in the areas, However, depending on circumstances, roadside vendors must comply with zoning and licensing restrictions, health and sanitation.
5. Problems face by consumers are ranked as a) Improper parking facility, b) Unhygienic Conditions of the tea stalls, c) Improper shelf space, d) Selling of other products, e) Unavailability of branded bakery items, f) Lack of knowledge of Retailers, g) Unavailability of desirable products, h) Billing Problems

Conclusion

This present study was conducted with a purpose of understanding the changes taking place in the minds of consumers towards modern formats and traditional. It was observed that due to the changing demographics, increase in DINKS families, urbanization, and awareness due to electronic media especially internet the customers have multiple options to choose. Majority of the consumers are visiting road site tea stall formats for variety, easy availability, cleanliness with quality and convenient parking facility etc. tea stalls, credit and bargaining facility balance the tilt. Unlike higher age groups who prefer to visit hotel for tea, the younger generation has more inclination towards road site tea stall. Customers with higher qualification were found to be more attracted towards tea stall . It is indicated that tea maker need to add more product lines and focus on quality as well as variety

A vital marketing strategy is the basis of a successful sales strategy. The roadside assistance businesses are fast-paced operations with little patience for long sales cycles. A thoroughly developed marketing plan helps to focus selling proposition and deliver messaging in channels that are well received by customer base. United with a sales plan, a marketing plan offers an effective selling strategy that converts prospects to customers. Stall owner and salesman are active players in selling to roadside assistance businesses.

Lastly “Chai is a common man’s drink”.

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